

IPBES Data Management Tutorials

IPBES task force on knowledge and data and the IPBES task force on capacity building
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Series Editors: Rainer M. Krug, Benedict D. Aboki Omare, Aidin Niamir
Series Contributors: Joy A. Kumagai, Håkon da Silva Hyldmo

Chapter Leads: Grégoire Dubois, Rainer M. Krug, Aidin Niamir, Hanno Seebens, David Thau
Chapter Contributors: Benedict D. Aboki Omare, Wouter Addink, Debora P. Drucker, Grégoire Dubois, Tim Hirsch, Rainer M. Krug, Joy A. Kumagai, Howard P. Nelson, Aidin Niamir, Fatima Parker-Allie, Hanno Seebens, David Thau

Description of Tutorials

The IPBES data management tutorials are short videos to help experts implement the IPBES data management Policy. They cover topics ranging from data management policy, reports, active research data, tools, and examples.

Overview of Chapters

- *Chapter 1. Introduction to IPBES data management tutorials*
 - Provides an overview on data management within the IPBES platform, and the series of the tutorials prepared by the task force on knowledge and data that will assist experts with the implementation of the IPBES data management policy.
 - DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4014762](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4014762)
- *Chapter 2. IPBES data management policy*
 - Provides an introduction of the IPBES data management policy. It discusses why IPBES has a data management policy and who is responsible for what in the implementation and further development of this policy.
 - DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4014790](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4014790)
- *Chapter 3. IPBES data management reports*
 - Provides an overview and discussion of specific elements of IPBES data management reports.
 - DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4014792](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4014792)
- *Chapter 4. Data management of active research data*
 - Provides an introduction for IPBES experts on how to manage data while actively being used, analyzed, and produced to fulfill the criteria of the IPBES data management policy.
 - DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4014796](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4014796)
- *Chapter 5. Tools for data management*

- Provides IPBES authors with an overview of open source tools used frequently by the scientific community to help it implement data management for the entire data life cycle.
- DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4014798](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4014798)

- *Chapter 6: Examples of implementing the IPBES data management Policy*
 - Contains examples of how certain data management tasks and workflows were implemented within IPBES so that they follow the data management policy. Over time, diverse examples from different assessments and other IPBES projects will be added.
 - DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4014802](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4014802)

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Contact:

If you have any questions or would like to provide feedback on these sessions please contact the technical support unit on knowledge and data at tsu.data@ipbes.net.